
COHERENT AI DECISION-MAKING WITH MULTIPLE SELVES

ABSTRACT

Humans make decisions by balancing evolving personal values and past experiences while maintaining a relatively stable sense of 'Self.' This coherence enables adaptive and robust responses to novel situations.

In this work, we hypothesize that maintaining a coherent sense of self is essential for robust AI decision-making. We introduce a framework where an AI agent is modeled as multiple sub-agents, each optimizing its own reward function. Coherence emerges when these sub-agents reach equilibrium, creating a unified sense of self. This approach seeks to enhance adaptability and decision-making robustness, inspired by human cognition.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advancing AI with human-like cognitive capabilities such as metacognition and a sense of self is critical for robust decision-making [1]. Humans naturally integrate evolving personal values and experiences, allowing them to make adaptive and consistent decisions in complex environments [2].

In this proposal we focus on bringing a sense of self into AI. Reduced or fragmented sense of self is associated with cognitive disorders such as PTSD and Autism Spectrum Disorders [3]. Similarly for AI to navigate complex environments, past experiences and associated rewards need to be integrated coherently.

We introduce a model for how a sense of self might emerge naturally in an AI agent, where multiple sub-agents (selves) operate with independent objectives. Each sub-agent might represent a belief an individual might have about a situation, which affects their decision-making.

To model this setup, we use a multi-agent reinforcement learning framework. A 'Self' agent with access to the value functions of each sub-agent, learns a distribution to sample from them, maximizing its expected reward. The sub-agents then update their policy to maximize their likelihood of being selected. We view this in game-theoretic notions, and define a coherent sense of self as When an equilibrium is reached in the strategies of the sub-agents.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 SENSE OF SELF AND AUTONOMY IN AI

Previous work on bringing high-level concepts into AI has mentioned issues such as self-awareness and metacognition [1], and sense of self [4],[5]. Modeling the overall self as set of objects has been explored in [5], but they do not consider the self as *multiple* agents, but as one agent with a set of rewards. More recent work of [6] in LLMs has also explored the effectiveness of taking into account multiple perspectives.

Cognitive dissonance.

2.2 HUMAN DECISION-MAKING BACKGROUND

Previous work in the neuroscience of decision making such as [2] has established that humans draw upon past experiences and rewards associated to them to make decisions. For example, the Hippocampus is believed to contribute significantly to decision-making by creating relevant records of the past memories [2].

More. Add something about the mosaic control model.

3 METHODOLOGY

We consider a game where the 'Self' agent aims to learn distribution over sub-agents, while each sub-agent aims to update its policy to make it more likely that it is selected.

The 'self' agent samples from a distribution over set of sub-agents. This Distribution is according to expected value of their policy in the current state of the world. So given state s it would sample from agent i with policy π_i Then it would observe values of each agent. It would then update β according to:

$$\max_{\beta} \sum_{\beta_i} \beta_i \mathbf{E}_s[V_i^{\pi_i}(s)]$$

Each sub-agent then maximizes its policy to maximize its reward. So it would have:

$$\pi_i^* = \max_{\pi_i} \beta_i$$

This can be seen as an instance of a multi-agent multi-armed adversarial bandit learning problem, as in [7], [8]. The adversary here is the self agent choosing the distribution over sub-agents, while each sub-agent aims to maximize its own reward.

A sense of self is maintained when the distribution of the play converges to the set of equilibrium points of the setup. One such equilibrium is that when averaged over the states of the world, each sub-agent is equally likely to be picked. So then no agent would gain from updating its policy. If all states are equally likely, this would correspond to all agents having the same policy.

In summary, we provide two main contributions:

- We demonstrate and motivate a strategy for an adversary choosing rewards for a set of sub-agents, aiming to improve decision-making.
- Borrowing ideas from the decision-making capabilities of humans, we model a coherent sense of self as the equilibrium points of a game whereby a self-agent rewards appropriate sub-agents.

4 DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

We note that this is different but similar to the problem of mixed policy reinforcement learning, as the self updates the distribution which maximizes a reward, but each agent updates its own independent policy to maximize the reward associated with being selected. We can look at the problem from the perspective of cognition consistency [9], where different agents are encouraged to share their understanding of their environment, resulting in enhanced cooperation.

For future work, we aim to consider more complex setups and scenarios. As an example, each sub-agent could have information about the rewards of the other sub-agents. The problem of adversarial inverse multi-agent RL [10] could be applied to this scenario, where each sub-agent would learn the policy of the sub-agents receiving the highest rewards. We note that to maintain the diversity of sub-agents, the self agent could regularize the distribution towards a uniform distribution.

5 RELEVANCE TO 2025 COOPERATIVE AI RESEARCH GRANT

This proposal introduces a framework for how cooperation *within* the components of an agent navigating complex situations can be relevant. It borrows ideas from human decision-making capabilities as a model for navigating complex strategies and, as such, is aligned with human strategies.

Our budget estimate is , and the estimated project length will be

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